

RTV and yield are shown in the table.

Jan-Apr 1984, RTV incidence was negligible and yields were high in all treatments. Jun-Oct 1985, plots treated with the oil mixture had significantly less RTV infection than the untreated

control (9% RTV), but yields were not significantly different. Nov 1984-Mar 1985, RTV incidence was significantly less in plots treated with the oil mixture than in insecticide-treated and untreated control plots. Yield was significantly

higher in plots treated with the oil mixture.

Net gain was consistently higher in plots treated with NO:CAO than in untreated or insecticide-treated plots. □

Ufra threatens deepwater rice in Majuli, Assam

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Ufra disease caused by stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* was severe in deepwater rice on Majuli, the river island of Brahmaputra in Assam. About 2,000 ha was badly damaged. Symptoms observed included the characteristic white patches of barren rice plants, panicles of many plants that did not emerge, or only half emerged, and stems of many plants that produced aborted skeletons of deformed panicles (see

Aborted panicles of rice due to stem nematode. Assam, India.

figure). Variety Padmapani appeared to escape the disease, probably because of

its early maturity (Nov). Popular variety Rangabao was severely affected.

Ufra problem in low-lying areas of Bangladesh

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We surveyed the disease situation of five low-lying areas during the 1986 aman (Apr-Dec). Three zones in the south, where ricefields are subjected to tidal submergence twice every 24 h, were found to be ufra prone (see figure).

Tidal water helps spread ufra

Outbreak of ufra disease in Bangladesh.